

BAMBOO-GUADUA ANGUSTIFOLIA KUNT FIBERS FOR GREEN COMPOSITES

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1 Summary

Extraction and tensile properties of fiber bundles of bamboo *Guadua Angustifolia kunt* are explored. Fiber bundles are extracted through chemical digestion processes with different contents of effective alkali (EA), sulfidity (S), and hydro-module (HM). Tensile tests were performed on the extracted fiber bundles to determine their modulus of elasticity and tensile strength. Digestion results indicate that increments of sulfidity at constant effective alkali results in better delignification processes. The obtained tensile properties are comparable to those of other natural fibers, and they exhibit a high variability preventing their deterministic definition. Therefore, a Log-Normal probability density function is proposed for the tensile strength and modulus of elasticity of *Guadua* fiber bundles, which can be easily incorporated into any micromechanical approach.

2 Introduction

Bamboo is a woody plant that belongs to the grass Poaceae family. A giant bamboo species, called *Guadua Angustifolia kunt* (G.A.K.), can be found in some countries of South and Central America. This giant grass has been used as a construction material [1]. However, the top part of the G.A.K., which has the highest concentration of fibers, is discarded because it has a small diameter.

Fig. 1. Cross section of culm wall

The culm of a bamboo plant is a ligno-cellulosic

natural functionally graded composite material. In the Figure 1 is possible to see that fibers are located densely around the outer cortex (region B) and separately in the inner surface (region A). In the inter-nodal region the fibers are aligned with the longitudinal axe of the plant, and in the nodal area are distributed with different orientations to transport nutrients from one side to the other. Extraction of bamboo fiber bundles without affecting their mechanical properties is not an easy task. Moreover, in the effort to remove all the lignin, the bamboo fibers properties can be affected, and may become brittle. Therefore, the massive use of bamboo fibers in reinforced composites requires the development of a simple and efficient method of extraction, while considering the potential impact of the chemical digestion process in their mechanical properties.

Natural fibers exhibit several advantages when compared to synthetic fibers, they are not only biodegradable and renewable resources but also exist in abundance, and particularly, bamboo is considered to be the last sustainable plant resource which has not been massively used [2,3]. Natural fibers are a good choice to be used as reinforcement material in polymeric composites because they have good mechanical properties and are easy to obtain. Literature shows that development of polymer composites reinforced with natural fibers involves four general areas of investigation: delignification and separation of fibers (chemical digestion process), mechanical characterization of the fibers, characterization of the polymer-fiber interaction, and evaluation of the composite effective properties. Several natural fibers have been studied for reinforcing polymeric matrices. However, bamboo fibers have not been a focus of investigation despite its amazing structural properties [1], fast growth, and biodegradability [2].

Some research has been performed to determine the mechanical properties of bamboo fibers. There is only one study on the mechanical properties of G.A.K. fibers, reporting values of 512 to 769 MPa for tensile strength, and 25 to 29 GPa for the modulus of elasticity [4]. Although, these results provide encouraging mechanical tensile properties, the authors do not describe the mechanical process employed for the fiber extraction, and the fibers from the upper zone of the G.A.K. were not studied. In order to define an efficient digestion process and to determine the tensile properties of the G.A.K. fibers suitable for composite materials, further research is required to fully understand the relationship between the extraction methods and the mechanical properties of the extracted fibers.

In the present work, fibers from the top part of the G.A.K. are extracted through a chemical digestion process using different concentrations of EA, S, and HM at controlled temperature and pressure. The chemical composition, physical, and mechanical properties of the extracted fiber bundles are characterized to explore their potential use in light-weight and low-cost polymeric composites, with adequate strength and stiffness for different applications. Tensile mechanical properties of G.A.K. fibers are experimentally determined, and they are for the first time fitted to a statistical distribution of probability density function to be used in micromechanical approaches.

3 Materials and Methods

The bamboo species used for this research was *Guadua angustifolia* kunt from Cauca Valley, Colombia. The 4-year-old bamboo culms used were cut from the top part of the plant, and then cut into 8 to 10 cm long, 0.5 to 3.0 cm wide, and 0.5 to 2 mm thick pieces, in order to have a better reagent soaked in the digestion.

3.1 Digestion

Selection of the adequate extraction process depends on the raw material (softwoods, hardwoods or not wood plants), equipment availability, and the required fiber integrity. There are several techniques for the extraction of natural fibers including mechanical, semi-mechanical, chemical-mechanical, thermomechanical, and chemical procedures. The last two processes allow the extraction of longer

fibers having the same mechanical properties as those obtained by mechanical and chemical-mechanical methods [5].

Alkaline and kraft processes are the two most common methods used in chemical pulping. The alkaline digestion process uses an aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (NaOH) at high temperatures. This process is time consuming (2 hours of cooking) with poor yields. On the other hand, the Kraft process is a modification of the alkaline process, in which the pulping is cooked in an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and sodium sulfide (Na₂S), called white liquor. The presence of sodium sulfide reduces the cooking time and stabilizes the cellulose. As a result, the fiber extracted from this process present less damages [6]. After the digestion, the fiber is separated by hand and thoroughly washed. The residual liquor, known as black liquor, is consider as a dangerous waste due to its content of reagents, lignin, hemicellulose, cellulose and some resins. Nevertheless, the black liquor could be treated by means of a combustion process using a furnace recovery boiler.

Table 1. Alkaline and kraft liquor cooking conditions.

Digestion	EA (%)	S (%)	HM (l/kg)	Kappa
F1	15	0	4	17.6
F2	15	0	15	18.7
F3	15	15	4	12.1
F4	15	15	15	10.8
F5	20	20	4	24.9
F6	20	20	15	19.5
F7	20	50	4	23.6
F8	20	50	15	19.6

In the present study, an autoclave model All-American 50X-120 was used for the digestion process at controlled pressure and temperature of 1.5 MPa and between 105 to 115°C, respectively. Alkaline and kraft processes were tried with different liquor conditions as shown in Table 1.

3.2 Mechanical Properties

Tensile test of bundles of G.A.K. fibers were performed based on ASTM C1557-03 [7] and ASTM D3822-07 [8] test procedures. Figure 2 shows the test specimen for the G.A.K. fiber bundle tensile tests. The fiber bundles were first air dried and then glued to a cardboard substrate, 24 hr before the test, using an epoxy resin adhesive similar to that

recommended in ASTM D3822-07 [8]. The test specimen gauge length (l_0) is measured to the nearest 0.5 mm, and then it is placed and aligned in the machine. After that, the cardboard material is cut in the assembly in the gage area without making contact with the fiber. The tests are conducted at a constant cross-head displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min with a 2.3 kg capacity load cell (LC509-005). The test is performed until fiber fracture is reached while recording both, the displacement and force of the cross-head.

Fig. 2. Fiber bundle specimen for tensile tests.

The specimens tested were fiber bundles and not single fibers because of the difficulty associated with extracting and testing very small fibers.

Mechanical properties of G.A.K. fiber bundles are determined by means of tensile tests. Calculation of the modulus of elasticity and tensile strength requires the measurement of the cross-sectional area of the fiber bundles. In this work, the areas of the cross sections of the fiber bundles were determined by direct measurements on micrographs of the failure surface from Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) (Figure 3). The shape of the cross section of the fiber bundles were in general not circular nor regular, as a consequence, the calculation of these areas were determined by image analysis.

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of fiber bundles cross section

Tensile properties of G.A.K fiber bundles exhibit high variability even for fibers extracted from the same plant. The modulus of elasticity varies from 8 to 150 GPa, while the tensile strength is in the range of 187 to 1152 MPa, with average coefficients of variation of 74.8 % and 44.4 %, respectively. This high variability in mechanical properties is observed for many natural fibers as reported by Symington et al. [9].

3 Analysis of Results and Conclusions

Tensile strength and elasticity modulus results yielded ranges of values exhibiting only slight differences among digestion conditions. This behavior prevents the direct evaluation of the best white liquor for the G.A.K. fiber bundles extraction in terms of the resulting mechanical properties. In order to determine the effects of EA, S, and HM on the mechanical properties of the extracted fibers, Pearson and Spearman correlations analyses were performed.

The relationship between tensile strength and EA is inversely proportional, that is, higher levels of EA result in lower tensile strength. This behavior is explained by the fact that the sodium hydroxide (NaOH) not only helps to the delignification process, but also attacks the cellulose in the plant, damaging the G.A.K. fiber bundles.

The modulus of elasticity E have a directly proportional relationship with S, higher E is obtained when the extraction process is performed at higher S concentrations.

Higher levels of sulfidity accelerate the delignification process, reducing the digestion time. Thus, the cellulose is exposed to the sodium hydroxide (NaOH) attack for less time and the result is a less damaged pulp. In contrast, the relationship between tensile modulus of elasticity and HM is inversely proportional, a higher HM results in lower E. This behavior can be explained since a higher HM implies a higher amount of chemical reagent per unit weight of row material.

The large dispersion obtained for the tensile properties of the G.A.K fiber bundles indicate that they should not be defined in a deterministic way. Instead, a statistical approach may be used to obtain a probabilistic distribution of the fiber tensile properties. Different probabilistic density functions

(pdf) were tested, and the best fit was with the Log-Normal distribution as shown in Figures 4 and 5.

Fig. 4. Tensile strength probabilistic density functions.

Fig. 5. Modulus of elasticity probabilistic density functions.

The resulting tensile strength and elasticity modulus distributions may be incorporated in any micromechanical approach to determine the effective properties of reinforced composites using G.A.K fiber bundles. Numerical simulations were performed to determine the equivalent properties of G.A.K. fiber reinforced composites. The obtained stiffness of bamboo reinforced composites are shown in Figure 6, where other PVC composites reinforced with different natural fibers and glass fiber are compared.

Fig. 6. Elastic modulus for PVC composites with different reinforcements.

The figure shows evidence of the bamboo *Guadua angustifolia kunt* fibers potential as reinforcement for polymers. It results remarkable that the G.A.K. reinforced composite is stiffer than fiberglass

composite with volume fractions lower than 50 %.

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